

Development of Higher Music Education in Kazakhstan: Historical Aspect

Mukasheva A. B.

Doctor of pedagogical sciences , Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Kazakhstan.

Khassanova S.A.

3rd year doctoral student, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Kazakhstan.

Galiyeva B. Kh.

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of Theoretical and Applied Linguistics of the Eurasian National University named after L.N. Gumilyov, , Kazakhstan.

Algozhayeva N.S.

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, associate professor, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Head of the Department of Pedagogy and Educational Management., Kazakhstan.

Imanbekova B.I.

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Kazakhstan.

Onalbekov E.S.

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Kazakhstan.

ABSTRACT: In modern society, there is a special interest in the history of nations, customs, traditions, and culture, since they reflect the unique national life and history. National culture is original, because it expresses the spiritual life of its nation through special, specific and original means and methods that form a systemic integrity.

The state's attention to the problems of reviving the historical past and cultural issues is confirmed by the adoption of the "Cultural Heritage" program. The development of this Program is dictated by the need for a more active, constructive impact on the situation in the field of cultural heritage. In its formation and development, higher music education in Kazakhstan has come a long way, undergoing certain changes and improving under the influence of political, economic and socio-cultural conditions of the development of society.

Nowadays, higher music education is developing in the context of those transformations that determine the development strategy of the entire higher education system in the Republic of Kazakhstan. In this regard, the process of training music pedagogical personnel in higher education in Kazakhstan requires a new approach, since society sets a global task - the professional training of competent, competitive specialists who meet international education standards.

Keywords: Higher Music Education, Development, Historical Aspect, Cultural Heritage.

Introduction

Methods

Literature Review

Conclusion

References

1. Introduction

At the present stage, a state policy in the field of education is being formed in Kazakhstan, the goal of which is a radical modernization of the education system to

increase its competitiveness, the development of human capital, ensuring sustainable economic growth and the well-being of citizens.

In the messages of the President of the country to the people of Kazakhstan, in the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "Education", the State Program "Education", and in other strategically important documents and legislative acts, the tasks of creating favorable conditions for identifying the creative potential of each individual, developing his individuality, and to the achievements of domestic and world culture, obtaining a quality education aimed at the formation, development and professional development of the individual.

In solving these problems, a special place is occupied by higher school, which is focused on training specialists with creative thinking, competent and competitive, able to demonstrate mobility in constantly changing socio-economic conditions.

At the same time, a modern system of continuous professional education cannot be created without knowing the history of education. Also, under estimating the historical approach to the study of culture and art leads to a misunderstanding of many phenomena in the spiritual life of society, including ineffective teaching and other negative consequences. In this article, the authors describe in detail the history of the development of higher music education in Kazakhstan during the period under study, which allows us to identify leading trends, reveal the features of the music education system at each stage of its development, propose new ways to improve higher music education, which can help solve pressing problems development of the system of higher music education in line with modern requirements.

2. Methods

The methodological basis of the study is made up of fundamental provisions about the cultural-historical theory of the development of society, the social essence of education, and the relationship in history of the past, present, and future. During analyzing and characterizing historical materials, we used systemic-structural, historical-cultural, socio-formational, holistic, integrated approaches. In addition, we relied on the methodological principles of historicism and objectivity, which ensured scientific objectivity and accuracy in covering the historical and pedagogical process of implementing higher music education in Kazakhstan.

3. Literature Review

Since ancient times, the musical education of the younger generation has been considered an integral part of life, traditions, and the foundations of society and reflects the peculiarities of the way of life of each nation. Creativity was generated by everyday necessity and the level of development of the people.

Even ancient philosophers, such as Aristotle and Plato, argued that the state could only be governed by musically educated citizens who were brought up in palaestras, choirs

and music. Confucius highly valued music, believing that it is music that can influence a person's moral character and character.

The outstanding music critic B.V. Asafiyev was convinced that the sphere of music is not only the composition of music and its performance, but also that it is connected with everyday life and with all the cultural achievements of mankind. He said that music is an art, a science, a language and a game, and that it can only breathe in full communication with the surrounding life, with its emotions and thoughts.

In the Kazakh steppe, music really breathed and flowed with its beautiful melody. Each folk song, *kyue*, expressed the life of the people, conveyed the feelings and thoughts that the singer or performer wanted to convey to the listener.

An analysis of the historical prerequisites for the development of higher music education in Kazakhstan showed that the rich Kazakh folk has musical creativity, the emergence of amateur groups, the opening of musical theaters, music schools and technical schools, the organization of singing lessons in secondary schools, the need for highly qualified musical personnel determined the origin and formation of higher musical education in Kazakhstan.

Historical and pedagogical analysis of archival materials, works of academic teachers, musicologists allowed us to divide the historiography on the problem under study within an established chronological framework into two main periods: Soviet (from 1944 to 1990) and post-Soviet (from 1991-to present). At the same time, an analysis of events and changes in higher music education showed that within each of the two identified periods there are relatively independent stages.

Main Part

Periods	Development of higher music education	Priority directions
1	2	3
1 period 1944 – 1959 – The origin and formation of higher music education in Kazakhstan.	Opening of the first higher musical educational institution, Alma-Ata State Conservatory named after Kurmangazy,	Training of highly qualified professional music pedagogical personnel. Composer's creativity
2 period 1960 – 1990. – The origin and formation of higher music education in Kazakhstan.	The opening of music departments at various faculties, and then music pedagogical faculties in pedagogical institutes. Organization of Art Institutes Institutes of Culture with the Faculty of Music.	Training of music teachers for secondary schools and highly qualified professional music teaching staff.
3 period 1991 – 2003 – Development of higher music education in the independent Republic of Kazakhstan	Development of higher education during the period of independence of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Destruction of Soviet ideology. Building a national education system Democratization and diversification of education. The international cooperation	The formation of a national musical system of higher education. Training of competitive innovative specialists. Updating the content of higher music education. Opening of educational institutions of international level, taking into account the continuity and continuity of education.

<p>4 period 2004 - present time Modernization of higher music education in the context of entering the global educational space.</p>	<p>Progressive development of higher professional education in the 21st century. Democratization and diversification of education. Expanding international cooperation. Further development of higher music education in accordance with international standards. Signing of the Bologna process.</p>	<p>Introduction of new teaching technology. Active international cooperation. Training of competitive, competent specialists taking into account foreign experience. Student exchange. International internships.</p>
---	---	---

The first stage (1944-1959) - is the origin and formation of higher music education in Kazakhstan.

The country's leadership, overcoming the difficulties of the war years, did not ignore science, culture and education. Evidence of this is the preservation of central higher educational institutions through their evacuation to safe areas of the country.

An analysis of historical materials showed that during the war, 12 evacuated universities from Moscow, Leningrad, Kyiv, Voronezh and others continued to operate in Almaty, which provided highly qualified assistance to Kazakh scientists and universities in organizing the educational process, research and political education work. The teaching staff of the evacuated central universities contributed to strengthening and improving the quality of educational and scientific work of higher educational institutions of the republic.

At the same time, despite the war and the economic and social problems associated with it, new higher educational institutions were opened in the country.

Thus, a progressive factor in the development of higher musical education in the republic was the opening in 1944 of the Alma-Ata State Conservatory, the first higher music institution.

At the same time, as an analysis of the Conservatory's activities shows, despite certain improvements, there were also difficulties caused by the post-war period. In particular, this concerned logistics and the lack of classroom funds. The most important problem was the lack of a dormitory; students lived in a barracks-type building, adapted as a dormitory, where there were only 17 rooms.

The opening of the theater department in the 1955/56 academic year aggravated the already difficult situation of the Conservatory, since for the full functioning of this department, auditoriums, a hall with a stage, props, costumes and much more were needed.

The lack of necessary conditions, insufficient musical training, and the professional incompetence of students from the theater department and some departments of music specialties led to a large dropout of students. Particularly low academic performance was observed in the theater department and the department of wind and string instruments.

In the late 50s and early 60s, education at the Conservatory was carried out by 15 departments, the teaching staff consisted of 112 main teachers. The fundamental task of the team in the field of scientific and methodological work was the creation of teaching aids, pedagogical repertoire programs, since there were not enough of them for preparatory courses, correspondence courses, music colleges and schools of the republic.

Thus, the first stage is characterized by the origin and formation of higher musical education, which was due to the opening of the first higher musical education. The

distinctive features of this stage were that all educational documents, the list of disciplines taught, and the development of the material and technical base were determined in accordance with the central educational policy of the USSR, which was carried out by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education. At the same time, the teachers of the Conservatory actively conducted research and created textbooks, the content of which introduced a national component, the repertoire list of programs was supplemented with works by national and Soviet composers of Kazakhstan.

The Second Stage (1960 - 1990) was characterized by us as an expansion of the system of higher music education. As an analysis of historical materials shows, music schools and the Conservatory could not provide the republic with musical and pedagogical personnel, which secondary schools especially lacked. For example, in the 1960/61 academic year, only 14 graduates of music schools in our republic arrived in secondary schools, and the number of graduates who arrived from pedagogical schools of the RSFSR and Ukraine was 37 people. Therefore, the huge demand and needs of the republic for competent teacher-musicians with higher education led to the opening of music departments in pedagogical universities of Kazakhstan with the aim of training highly qualified music teachers.

Thus, in the 1960/61 academic year, a music department with a four-year course of study was opened at the Kazakh State Women's Pedagogical Institute at the Faculty of Philology. In 1967, the Kazakh composer, Honored Artist Bakhytzhan Baikadamov, organized a music pedagogical faculty at the institute with four departments: history and theory of music, choral conducting, musical education, musical instruments. The faculty trained singing and music teachers for Kazakh schools. Due to the fact that students without initial musical training entered the faculty and studied, teachers faced enormous difficulties in teaching female students. But, nevertheless, with great effort, the music and pedagogical faculty of the Women's Pedagogical Institute provided Kazakh schools in remote areas of the republic with music teachers.

Thus, the second stage is characterized by the expansion of the system of higher music education through the opening of music sections, departments and music pedagogical faculties in the pedagogical institutes of the republic with the aim of training highly qualified music teachers for secondary schools.

The intensive development and improvement of the system of higher music education was due to the political, economic and cultural development of Soviet society. During these years, there has been an increase in the material and technical support of educational institutions, improvement of the content, forms, methods and means of teaching, improvement of the qualifications of musical personnel, the opening of music schools, colleges, etc. All this was the basis for the further development and improvement of higher music education in the republic.

At the same time, during the Soviet period we observed increased ideologization and politicization of education, unification of educational programs, and financing of education on a residual basis.

The Third Stage (1991 – 2003) - development of higher music education in the Republic of Kazakhstan in new socio-economic conditions.

This stage is characterized by the formation of the Republic of Kazakhstan as an independent state, the collapse of the USSR empire, and, as a consequence, the destruction of Soviet ideology. Accordingly, the political and economic transformations that took place in the Republic of Kazakhstan were reflected in the education system, which led

to innovative transformations. Kazakhstan was building its national education system. Over the years of independence of the Republic of Kazakhstan, a legislative and regulatory framework has been established in the higher education system; modernization of the higher education system, updating its content. The Concept of State Policy in the Field of Education was developed (August 4, 1995); from 1995 to 1997, the first Kazakhstan educational standards were adopted for 310 specialties of higher professional education.

In 1996, a new edition of the Classifier (list) of specialties in higher education of the Republic of Kazakhstan was approved, providing for 342 specialties. The development of the non-state education sector has contributed to an increase in the number of students studying in higher educational institutions, including in music (Academic Innovation University, Bolashak University, Kostanay Social and Technical University, Syrdarya University, South Kazakhstan Pedagogical University, Kazakh-Chinese Institute, International Humanitarian and Technical University).

There has been decentralization of management and financing of education, expansion of academic freedom of educational organizations: the principles of admission to higher educational institutions have changed, a transition has been made to the training of specialists with higher professional education on the basis of the state educational order. Since 1999 - provision of state educational grants and state educational loans to applicants on a competitive basis. Since 2001, the strategic development of the system of higher and secondary education has begun: the main directions for the progressive development of higher professional education in the 21st century have been determined. All these gradual changes in the education system as a whole undoubtedly affected the system of higher music education. For example, in the early 90s, in connection with the revival of folk customs and traditions, some work was done in higher musical educational institutions to train specialists in the field of traditional musical art.

At the same time, it was in the 90s that significant changes occurred related to the training of personnel, including music, in educational institutions of predominantly university type, which met international standards.

A major political and economic step in 1998 was the transfer of the capital to Astana. For the region of central Kazakhstan and the north of the republic, this step became a rebirth. It contributed to the growth of the republic's economy, changing the appearance of regional centers, intensive construction was underway, thousands of new jobs were created, and the cultural life of the capital was improving.

So, on the initiative and with the support of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan N.A. Nazarbayev, on March 31, 1998, the Kazakh National Academy of Music (KazNAM) was formed in Astana, a unique educational institution that takes into account a comprehensive system with end-to-end continuous education, within the walls of which a new generation of highly professional specialists in the field of musical art is educated and trained. The best traditions of domestic education and upbringing of youth, recognized throughout the world, are integrated with modern achievements of the global educational process. The Academy pays great attention to gifted children from all regions of Kazakhstan, creating the necessary conditions for comprehensive education and training of a new generation of art masters. The Academy has become a promising cultural and educational center for the promotion of world art and Kazakh music.

The Kazakh National Academy of Arts named after T. Zhurgenov opened the Department of Variety Art in 2000. The creation of a professional pop school and conditions for training specialists in this genre has become a strategically important step for Kazakhstan.

The Kazakh National Conservatory named after Kurmangazy, being the oldest higher musical educational institution, does not lag behind the requirements of the time. The international educational program "Rising Stars" is being introduced, the goal of which is to search for young talents and support the best participants for their further creative growth. This form of training is very popular in Europe and the USA. The information space and international activities at the university have expanded. Faculty and student orchestras travel to the CIS countries and abroad to exchange experiences, participate in various competitions, festivals, projects and conferences.

An analysis of the development of higher music education during the years of independence of the Republic of Kazakhstan showed that with the advent of the Classifier of Specialties and the state standard in the mid-90s, there is no such diversity in the names of musical specialties that was inherent at the beginning of the organization of music pedagogical education in pedagogical universities of the country ("Music and singing", "Music and choreography", "Methods of primary education with an additional specialty of music", etc.).

Analyzing scientific research, government documents, including standards of higher music education, we came to the conclusion that in relation to music education, competence is the possession of knowledge, skills and abilities in musical performance, mastery of knowledge in theoretical disciplines, major and general scientific subjects. And most importantly - the practical and psychological-pedagogical skills that he acquires in the process of teaching and performing practice.

Thus, the third stage is characterized by the formation of the Republic of Kazakhstan as an independent state, the destruction of Soviet ideology, and the formation of a national system of higher musical education. In this regard, at the present stage, the goal of higher music education is aimed at training competitive, competent specialists. There have been changes in the organization of educational institutions, management and standardization of learning processes, bringing the Classifier of Specialties closer to the international standard, expanding the integration potential of higher music education, the active introduction of innovative methods and forms of teaching, and the development of lifelong education.

The Fourth Stage (2004- to present) – modernization of the system of higher music education in the context of entering the global educational space.

In February 2004, the government of Kazakhstan approved the concept for the development of the education system of the Republic of Kazakhstan until 2015. Based on the Concept, the State Program for the Development of Education in the Republic of Kazakhstan until 2010 was developed. According to the State Program for the Development of Education for 2005-2010, many universities in Kazakhstan, including music ones, have made a transition to the credit system of education accepted in world practice, one of the advantages of which is the increased activity and independence of students in cognitive activity. For example, since 2004, the Conservatory has been systematically switching to a credit education system (art management, pedagogy and psychology of music education), and opening new departments and specialties. Also in the 2004/05 academic year, ZhenPI switched to a credit education system. In those same years, the first steps were taken towards the introduction of international requirements for personnel training - the transition to a multi-level system of "bachelor's - master's - PhD".

In order to improve the quality of the educational process, since 2004, in universities of Kazakhstan, including music ones, the "Quality Management" system has been officially introduced, within the framework of which planning, management, and evaluation of the

results and quality of education are carried out, in accordance with the requirements of the international standard.

During this period, Kazakhstani universities are actively participating in international cooperation, which is due to the dictates of the times. The Conservatory, for example, cooperates with the European Association of Conservatories and Higher Music Schools headquartered in Paris, the International Association of Music of Turkic Peoples, the International Academy of Sciences of Pedagogical Education, the International Summer Academy of Music Management, is a member of the International Council on Traditional Music, etc.

The University of Arts cooperates with the Moscow State Conservatory. P.I. Tchaikovsky, carries out mutually beneficial contacts with the Academies of Music in Paris, Helsinki, Croatia and intends to expand connections with other educational institutions, practice international experience in internships, seminars, festivals. The Academy of Music joined the Association of European Conservatories, Academies and Higher Schools of Music (AES).

Today, education is recognized as one of the most important priorities of the long-term Development Strategy of the Republic "Kazakhstan - 2050". In light of the reform of education at all its levels, in particular the determination of strategic ways for the development of music education at the present stage, is the preparation of music pedagogical personnel for 12-year schools. In particular, this concerns the training of music teachers in pedagogical universities who will participate in the implementation of this project. In this regard, the question arises about the quality of music teacher training when organizing specialized schools.

At the same time, in the development of higher music education, we note some progressive steps taken in the Republic of Kazakhstan in order to improve the content and scientific and theoretical foundations of higher music education. In particular, the project "Development of Music Education in the Republic of Kazakhstan" for 2017-2023, being implemented in the Republic of Kazakhstan, involves the development of a concept for the modern development of music education based on the synthesis of the existing national educational system and the recognized experience of world musical institutions.

The goal of this project is to develop music education and create a model of a world-class creative university. In accordance with the goal, the objectives indicate educational infrastructure, regulatory framework, care for masters and creative youth, the image and prestige of Kazakhstan's music education, fundamental and practice-oriented research, etc. The project provides for three strategic directions: improving pre-university musical training and creating a system of general aesthetic development of children and youth; modernization of higher music education and presentation of the national system of music education abroad.

In this context, the idea of creating an experimental school-studio of arts at the Kazakh National Conservatory named after Kurmangazy, expanding specialties, is a progressive and timely step. For example, new specialties: "Art management", "Music criticism", "Variety and jazz performance", "Musical psychology", "Repair and production of musical instruments" and even the training of home teachers and tutors with a musical education - all this is in demand at labor market.

Thus, the analysis of this stage and the results of the study showed that universities in Kazakhstan respond in a timely manner to the dynamically developing situation in the professional sphere and are ready to take into account the social needs of society. The

fourth stage is characterized by the organization of a multi-level system (bachelor's - master's - PhD) training of competitive, competent music pedagogical personnel of the new formation, taking into account foreign experience. In connection with the entry of the education system of the Republic of Kazakhstan into the global educational space, international cooperation, student exchange and international internships for teaching staff have intensified.

4. Conclusion

Our historical and pedagogical study of the development of higher music education in the period from 1944- to present allowed us to draw the following conclusions:

1. The historical prerequisite for the development of higher music education in Kazakhstan was the progressive socio-economic development of society. The creativity and activities of folk composers, the formation of creative groups, the opening of musical theaters, as well as the organization of singing lessons in secondary schools and the opening of primary and secondary music education institutions, in which the Kazakh intelligentsia, figures of musical art and culture of Kazakhstan took an active part, determined the origin and formation of higher musical education in our republic.
2. The formation and development of higher music education is associated with historical stages that determined the development paths of higher music education. In higher music education, during the period we studied from 1944-to present , significant changes occurred, which were directly related to changes in the political, economic and cultural life of the country.
3. During the period under study, a system of music education in the Republic of Kazakhstan was formed, in which continuity and continuity are observed.
4. The study of the history of the development of higher music education has shown that almost from the very inception, it is in music education in the preparation of performing musicians and music teaching staff that we observe the consideration of the national-regional and ethnocultural component. For example, dombra, kobyz, etc. were introduced into the list of specialties; the Kazakh folk orchestra was organized; Musicologists and music teachers specially collected and studied the works of folk composers, which were further processed and introduced into the content of the programs not only of the folk instruments department, but also replenished the repertoire list of programs of the conducting, choral, orchestral, piano departments, as well as theoretical disciplines.
5. Analysis of the content of higher music education showed that during the Soviet period it was unified and ideological. All curricula and programs, the list of disciplines taught, the development of the material and technical base were determined in accordance with the central educational policy of the USSR, which was carried out by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education. During this period, certain steps were taken to improve the content of education and bring it into line with scientific achievements: the creation of special repertoire councils for the selection of works, the publication of educational and musical aids, collections, and anthologies. Methods, forms and means of teaching were actively used, which contributed to the improvement of knowledge, abilities, skills, as well as performance skills.
6. During the period of independence of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the content of education was determined by the state standard, which clearly outlined the goals and objectives of the training of music pedagogical personnel and their competencies. Corresponding changes have occurred in the design of educational

and professional programs: they are completely freed from communist ideology, they take into account the national and regional characteristics of the education system, elective subjects were introduced, more time was devoted to independent work of students, etc.

7. In the process of identifying the main trends characteristic of the stages studied, leading trends were identified that open up the possibility of progressive development of higher music education, which are:
 - compliance of higher music education with the current needs of professional and secondary schools, determined by political, economic and socio-cultural factors in the development of society;
 - continuity and continuity of music education, and in the future the opening of innovative higher music educational institutions with continuous training;
 - strengthening the role of national-regional and ethnocultural components in the training of performing musicians and music teaching staff;
 - orientation of higher music education towards modern achievements in the field of science, technology, production and culture;
 - humanization and democratization, diversification, informatization, computerization, globalization of the system of higher music education in modern conditions.
8. Analysis and generalization of positive experience in the organization and further development of higher music education in Kazakhstan gave us the opportunity to outline the following ways of improvement:
 - It is necessary to develop a long-term state program for the development of higher music education in the Republic of Kazakhstan.
 - In connection with the transition to 12-year education in general education schools and the development of specialized schools, it is necessary to improve the training of music pedagogical personnel with a high level of knowledge of teaching methods and innovative technologies.
 - Creative and pedagogical universities of the republic, which in the role of resource centers will interact with secondary schools and various creative specialized schools, extracurricular institutions, need to develop a cooperation program that meets international standards.
 - In order to develop musical education and education of the younger generation, revive and develop musical culture in rural areas, provide targeted grant support for the most gifted rural youth.
 - In order to improve the quality of learning foreign languages by music teaching staff, it is necessary to develop special programs and strengthen material and technical equipment.
 - In order to develop modern composing creativity, train competent musical and pedagogical personnel, improve knowledge, skills and abilities in the use of computer technologies in the creative and practical activities of students. Taking into account the specifics of music education, develop innovative music-computer programs in computer science for students of music universities.
 - In modern conditions of globalization of music education, it is necessary to strengthen international ties for the exchange of students and teachers, provide for the organization and development of double-diploma music education, expand forms of international cooperation, grant support for international internships, especially in pedagogical universities.
 - In order to improve the quality of training of highly qualified, competitive specialists, it is necessary to develop a program of short-term additional education and distance learning.

Thus, the results of the study, obtained on the basis of a historical analysis of a large number of materials, taking into account their novelty and practical significance, are a

concrete contribution to the theory and practice of higher music education in modern conditions. Prospects for further research can be aimed at studying the organization of higher music education in regional universities of the Republic of Kazakhstan, studying the system of higher music education in the conditions of integration, computerization and globalization of education, studying innovative technologies for training competitive specialists with music education that meet international standards.

5. References

1. Danabayev, Kakim & Park, Jowon & Konieczny, Piotr Bronislaw (2021) . Q-Pop, the Pride of Kazakh Youth, and its Stimulation of Ethnic Identity. Doctoral dissertation. Seoul: Hanyang University.
2. Dobrovolskaya, L. V. (2014) Musical Traditions of the Kazakh People: Past and Present. Actual Problems of the Humanities and Natural Sciences, Vol. 11, No. 1, pp. 1–3.
3. Dossanova, Kamila K. & Kunekova, Tursyn M. & Zhumasheva, Gulzhan K. & Dossanova, (2018.) National Identity in the Modern Education of Kazakhstan.
4. Mukasheva A.B. (2009). Musical education and aesthetic education of students in secondary schools in Kazakhstan (to the history of the issue) // Social and humanitarian sciences. - No. 1-2. - pp. 168-170.
5. Mukasheva A.B (2009.) From the history of the organization of music education in secondary schools of Kazakhstan // Bulletin of the Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Kazakhstan. - No. 6 (33). - P. 51-56.
6. Mukasheva A.B. (2019) Historical aspects of the development of higher musical education in Kazakhstan // Bulletin of Al-Farabi KazNU. Series Pedagogical Sciences. No. 3 (28). - pp. 22-28.
7. Mukasheva A.B. (2019) The role of music schools in the training of music pedagogical personnel in Kazakhstan // Bulletin of Al-Farabi KazNU. Series Pedagogical Sciences. No. 3 (28.). - P. 96-100.
8. Kaztuganova, A. & Omarova, A. & Turmagambetova, B. & Kasimova, Z. & Kuzembay, S.(2019)
9. Kazakh Music in the Global Context. Utopia y Praxis Latinoamericana, Vol. 24, No. 5, pp. 90–102.
10. President of the Republic of Kazakhstan (1996.) Decree of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 2995 On the Concept of Forming the State Identity of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Available at <http://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/N960002995/links>, last accessed on 15 October 2022